

Evaluating the Impact of Macroeconomic Variables, Economic Policy
Uncertainty, and Financial Market Volatility on Clean Energy Stock Prices: A
Machine Learning Approach

Undergraduate Dissertation

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Abstract

Climate change represents a critical challenge to global stability and economic growth, mandating an essential transition from traditional fossil fuels to sustainable energy alternatives. As nations around the world advance towards low-carbon economic structures, clean energy equities have emerged as particularly attractive investment opportunities. This study uses machine learning methods to predict the direction of clean energy stock prices. Furthermore, given the limited existing literature, this study also explores the impact of fundamental macroeconomic variables, global economic policy uncertainty, and financial market volatility on predicting clean energy stock prices. The analysis reveals several important findings. First, Random Forests and Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) predict price directions with a higher degree of accuracy than Support Vector Machine and Naïve Bayes models. When assessing 15-day to 20-day forecasts, Random Forests reaches an accuracy threshold between 87% to 95%. Second, technical indicators, namely RSI and MACD are, on average, the features most important for predicting clean energy stock prices. Third, among non-technical indicators, economic policy uncertainty and the CBOE Volatility Index are ranked highly in importance. Across all datasets analysed, the US Consumer Price Index ranks the lowest, suggesting that clean energy stocks may not be effective as inflation hedges.

Keywords: Machine Learning, Forecasting, Clean Energy Stock Prices, Macroeconomic Variables, Renewable Energy, Policy Uncertainty, Volatility

1. Introduction

In the face of global climate challenges, it becomes imperative for nations to intensify their efforts in reducing carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions. In 2022, global CO₂ emissions experienced a resurgence, reaching 36.8 gigatons (Gt) after a brief decline during the peak of the COVID-19 pandemic (IEA, 2023). The following year, 2023, emissions increased further by 1.1 percent, crossing the 40 Gt threshold (IEA, 2024). The increase in global temperatures caused by elevated atmospheric CO₂ levels is already being felt. In the second half of 2023, the global average temperature exceeded the critical 1.5°C threshold on 182 out of 184 days spanning from July 1, 2023, to January 1, 2024 (Copernicus, 2023). This rise in temperature corresponds with a 'short-term El Niño influence' that raised 2023's global warming to 1.48°C above pre-industrial levels (Copernicus, 2023).

The surpassing of the 1.5°C global temperature threshold underscores the critical need for enhanced actions in both mitigation and adaptation strategies to prevent further rises in temperature. The UAE Consensus, presented at COP28 in December 2023, emphasises that to maintain global warming within 1.5°C with minimal overshoot, it is imperative to achieve substantial, prompt, and continuous reductions in worldwide greenhouse gas emissions (McKinsey & Company, 2024). Specifically, it calls for a 43% reduction by 2030 and a 60% reduction by 2035 compared to levels in 2019, aiming for net-zero CO₂ emissions by the year 2050 (McKinsey & Company, 2024).

Building on the urgency outlined by the UAE Consensus at COP28, the recent energy crisis has brought attention to the significant challenges that lie ahead. The increased number of bottlenecks in manufacturing, labour, investments, material availability, affordability, and land availability could slow down the energy transition (Loock, 2020). Furthermore, the development of capital markets has also led to high valuations for energy companies with fossil fuel-focused strategies, driven by 4x to 6x higher profits in 2022 compared to the pre-COVID-19 average between 2017 and 2019 (McKinsey & Company, 2024). At the same time, renewable energy players' profits are under pressure due to the difficult post-pandemic macroeconomic environment, including material inflation and capital cost increases. Macroeconomics plays a crucial role in the future expansion of clean energy initiatives, with 2024 likely to be a crucial year to see if further policy interventions, and corporate investment decisions can help maintain and build out the momentum of the transition.

Importantly, since the beginning of the 21st century, clean energy finance has received significant attention among researchers, for several reasons. Firstly, investments in the clean energy sector have experienced a notable surge leading to the emergence of clean energy stocks as a vital asset class in contemporary financial markets and the creation of a new avenue for clean energy equity investing. Figure 1 provides an overview of the development of annual financial commitments in the renewable energy sector. In 2023 alone, global investments in energy transition surged to a new high of \$1.77 trillion, marking a 17% increase from the prior year (BloombergNEF, 2024). This investment includes renewable power, nuclear, grids, storage, low-emission fuels, efficiency improvements and end-use renewables and electrification. Secondly, the escalating apprehensions regarding climate change and its prospective ramifications on economic and societal welfare are prompting a pressing demand for scholarly investigation in this domain. Third, there is an increased level of policy support through regulatory measures such as the US Inflation Reduction Act and new initiatives in Europe, Japan, the People's Republic of China, and other regions. Moreover, there is a specific emphasis on industrial strategy as countries aim to strengthen their positions in the growing clean energy sector (IEA, 2023). Fourthly, since the adoption of the Paris Climate Agreement at the 21st Conference of the Parties in 2015, environmental, social, and governance (ESG) issues have become more important than ever. Eco-friendly and socially responsible investors intend to participate in clean energy sectors in order to yield on low carbon portfolios. Lastly, whether green energy stocks can hedge traditional and non-traditional asset classes is of paramount interest to investors and policymakers.

Figure 1: Global Investments in Energy Transition from 2014 to 2023 (BloombergNEF, 2024)

Against this backdrop, this study extends the literature in several ways. First, this is the first empirical paper to account for the impact of macroeconomic variables on predicting clean energy stock prices. This empirical investigation reveals information on the relationship between stock prices and the following macroeconomic factors: interest rates (using the United States 10-Year Bond Yield), inflation (using the United States Consumer Price Index), foreign exchange volatility (using Deutsche Bank's CVIX), commodity volatility (using the S&P GSCI), economic policy uncertainty (using the EPU Index) and the effect of economic shocks (using the Citigroup Economic Surprise Index). Critically, predicting the direction of clean energy stock prices is relevant and important as investors are more interested in the direction of asset prices rather than the actual values when determining portfolio asset allocations (Pesaran & Timmermann, 2022).

Second, the paper adopts advanced machine learning methodologies to predict the price direction of clean energy stocks. A substantial body of literature indicates that machine learning methods tend to provide superior predictive accuracy compared to traditional econometric methodologies. Specifically, in cases where the relationship between the predicted variable and its features are complex (James et al., 2013; Mullainathan & Spiess, 2017). Drawing from the foundation provided by previous studies, the current paper employs various machine learning methodologies such as Random Forests, eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), Support Vector Machines (SVM), and Naïve Bayes.

Third, the features (explanatory variables or predictors) include technical indicators and the non-technical variables listed above. The significance of technical indicators in predicting asset prices is widely recognised in existing literature (Bustos and Pomares-Quimbaya, 2020, Sadorsky, 2022a, Sadorsky, 2021a, Sadorsky, 2021b, Wang et al., 2020, Yin and Yang, 2016). Fourth, the paper conducts a novel comparative analysis of feature importance from a machine learning perspective in the context of stock price forecasting. Investors avoid adopting machine learning models because of the lack of interpretability and dependability. However, the SHAP value method used in this study, combined with the accurate machine learning models, may be used by experts in making real-world decisions (Chakraborty et al., 2021).

Lastly, employing the Naïve Bayes classification as a robustness benchmark allows for a comparative analysis of feature importance from a fundamental statistical perspective, in contrast to more contemporary methods, such as Random Forests. This approach facilitates

a deeper understanding of the underlying dynamics and contributes to a more informed selection of models and features for predictive accuracy in various applications.

The objectives of this study are as follows: (a) evaluate and compare the effectiveness of various machine learning algorithms in forecasting, with the aim of identifying the most reliable methods for predictive analysis across different forecasting horizons; (b) investigate the impact of key macroeconomic factors on the prediction of clean energy stock prices, emphasising the identification of the most influential predictors; (d) analyse how the significance of predictor variables differs across multiple datasets; (e) synthesise the findings to provide actionable insights for both researchers and investment professionals.

The rest of the paper will be organised as follows. Section 2 reviews the related literature. Section 3 and 4 describes the data that is considered in the empirical analysis and in-depth description of the machine learning methods used in the analysis. The results are reported in Section 5. Section 6 concludes the paper and offers some practical implications stemming from the results.

2. Literature Review

This section presents a discussion on the existing literature that explores the relationship between macroeconomic variables, policy-induced uncertainties, and the volatility of financial markets on clean energy stock prices. Central to this research is the strategic application of machine learning (ML) techniques, which have revolutionised predictive analytics in finance. This critical literature examination extends beyond the simple comparison of ML algorithms; it aims to highlight the most accurate and widely used methodologies that can be adapted over temporal forecasting horizons.

The current body of literature on clean energy finance predominantly focuses on the dynamic interplay between the stock prices of clean energy companies, oil prices, and the stock prices of technology companies (Bondia et al., 2016, Dutta, 2017, Dutta et al., 2018, Elie et al., 2019a, Elie et al., 2019b, Ferrer et al., 2018, Geng et al., 2021, Gupta, 2017, Henriques and Sadorsky, 2008, Kumar et al., 2012, Le et al., 2021, Maghyereh et al., 2019, Managi and Okimoto, 2013, Naeem et al., 2020, Nasreen et al., 2020, Pham, 2021, Pham, 2019, Reboredo, 2015, Reboredo et al., 2017a, Reboredo et al., 2017b, Reboredo and Ugolini, 2018, Sadorsky, 2012, Saeed et al., 2021, Uddin et al., 2019, Wen et al., 2014). These investigations collectively reveal that the sector is influenced by complex interdependencies between various factors, including both systematic and idiosyncratic. Nevertheless, there exists two significant gaps in the current literature. Firstly, there is a lack of research dedicated to the forecasting of clean energy stock prices. Secondly, there is a shortage of comprehensive analysis of the impact of macroeconomic factors on clean energy stock prices. Notably, there is a complete absence of scholarly work in this domain that examines how these macroeconomic factors influence the forecasting of clean energy stock prices.

Within this context, only two papers, namely Sadorsky (2022a) and Sadorsky (2022b), have ventured into forecasting clean energy stock prices utilising modern econometric methodologies. Sadorsky (2022a) uses random forests (RFs) and support vector machines (SVMs) to forecast solar stock prices, demonstrating that these methods, along with extremely randomised trees and tree bagging, outperform traditional models like logit and boosted logit. Specifically, random forests achieve a prediction accuracy of approximately 89% at a 20-day forecasting horizon, while extra trees reach 92.4%. The feature set includes technical indicators and the volatilities of oil and silver prices, with technical indicators being the most influential predictors. The volatility of oil and silver prices rank in the top third of

feature importance. However, the study's limitations are noteworthy, as it relies only on one dataset, the Invesco Solar ETF (TAN), and limits its feature space to technical indicators and two types of commodity volatility. It is crucial to consider expanding the feature set to include non-technical predictors such as policy uncertainty, which Assereto & Byrne (2020) identify as a more significant factor in renewable versus non-renewable energy investment decisions. Sadorsky (2022b) expands on his earlier work by applying the same methodology to forecast clean energy stock prices using three ETFs: PBW, ICLN, and QCLN. He also addresses a limitation of his previous study by analysing the impact of economic policy uncertainty and market volatility using Shapley values. The study also finds that random forests and Extra Trees models yield higher predictive accuracy when compared to logistic regression and Naive Bayes models. It highlights that technical indicators, especially WAD, MA200, and MA500, are most important in forecasting, while market volatility (VIX) and oil price volatility (OVX) are significant non-technical predictors. However, the paper does not fully explore macroeconomic factors like economic growth, inflation, and interest rates, which have been shown to influence the clean energy sector significantly (Shah et al., 2018; Rathnayake et al., 2023). Including these macroeconomic indicators could provide a more detailed understanding of how business cycle conditions affect clean energy stock predictability. The paper could further improve its evaluation of model accuracy by including metrics that assess how well the model discriminates between positive ("up" days) and negative ("down" days) stock movements across different thresholds. Metrics such as AUC (Area Under the Curve) has been highlighted as a more robust metric compared to traditional accuracy metrics in evaluating machine learning models (Bradley, 1997; Demetriou et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2022).

The role of machine learning in stock price prediction is well-documented across many academic studies. Machine learning is particularly used for processing large and complex datasets, recognising patterns, and forecasting outcomes without the strict assumptions about data distribution required by traditional econometric methods. Given the inherent complexities of the stock market, this study employs machine learning to leverage its analytical capabilities. Research by Ampomah et al. (2020) utilises a range of machine learning classifiers, including Random Forests (RFs), XGBoost, Bagging, AdaBoost, ExtraTrees, and Voting Classifiers to forecast the direction of stock prices for six US stocks and two US stock exchanges. The study uses principal components analysis to select features from 40 technical indicators. The models demonstrated high accuracy, with results ranging

from 82% to 90%. Notably, the ExtraTrees and RF model consistently yielded the highest accuracy. Furthermore, research conducted by Hu et al. (2022) provides a comprehensive analysis on the effectiveness of different machine learning approaches in forecasting stock prices. The study examines the accuracy of LightGBM, Random Forest and Logistic Regression on three stocks to verify the consistency of results. The results indicate that the models' prediction performance varies significantly between short and long-time windows. This variation offers a significant research opportunity to further explore in this study, particularly in examining how the accuracy of each model varies across different forecasting horizons. Lohrmann and Luukka (2019) analysed S&P 500 stock price movements by classifying them into four directional categories based on the difference between opening and closing prices. They selected features using various technical indicators. Their findings highlighted that RF outperformed both decision trees and K-Nearest Neighbours (KNN) in accuracy. Trading signals generated from the RFs resulted in superior portfolio performance compared to a traditional buy-and-hold strategy. Lastly, Weng et al. (2018) employed several machine learning models including boosted regression trees, RFs, Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), and SVM to predict stock prices for twenty major US companies. They integrated non-traditional features such as data from social media (web page views), sentiment analysis of financial news, and search trends into their analysis. Their results showed that Random Forests and boosted regression trees significantly outperformed ANNs and SVMs in terms of prediction accuracy.

This study aims to address the limitations identified in the foundational research on clean energy forecasting conducted by Sadorsky (2022a, 2022b). By examining the gaps in these key studies, this study aims to explore four key feature spaces: (1) technical indicators, (2) macroeconomic variables, (3) economic policy uncertainty and (4) market volatility. These dimensions are critical for developing a comprehensive understanding of how business cycle conditions influence stock price movements. From the literature presented in the previous paragraph, it is clear that technical indicators are frequently utilised as features in directional stock price prediction.

Macroeconomic variables such as inflation, exchange rate volatility, and interest rates are critical factors affecting clean energy initiatives and consumption. These economic conditions in turn significantly influence clean energy stock prices. A study by Alam & Murad (2020) investigates the short-term and long-term impacts of economic growth, trade openness and technological progress on renewable energy use in OECD countries. Based on

43 years of data and using an autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) approach, the empirical results reveal that economic growth, trade openness and technological progress significantly influence renewable energy use over the long-term in OECD countries. Another paper by Deka et al (2021) investigates the causal link among the use of renewable energy, rate of currency exchange and the rate of inflation of Brazil with an ARDL model. The paper finds that the effect of the rate of inflation can impact currency exchange rates, which in turn affects the use of renewable energy. From their analysis, it is important to recognise that while the direct impact of inflation on clean energy stock prices may appear of weak importance, its effects are often mediated through other variables such as exchange rate volatility, which may exhibit a higher importance in feature rankings. Interest rates also play a crucial role in influencing clean energy projects. Ghosh (2022) explores the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on clean energy stocks, focusing on how interest rate changes have influenced their market performance. The paper shows that low interest rates can provide momentum for the development of clean energy projects. This is crucial as the cost of capital is a key factor in determining the feasibility and attractiveness of investments in renewable energy. Lower interest rates can make clean energy projects more financially viable and attractive to investors, thus promoting the growth of the clean energy sector. This body of research illustrates that macroeconomic variables such as inflation, exchange rate volatility, and interest rates are pivotal in shaping the dynamics of the clean energy sector and should be factored into this study's predictive analysis.

Economic policy uncertainty, including uncertainty about fiscal, monetary, and regulatory policies, can significantly impact business decisions and financial markets (Baker et al., 2016). When faced with such uncertainty, businesses often hesitate to commit to capital expenditures, which can adversely affect both current and future productivity and profitability (Pástor & Veronesi, 2012). Literature shows that economic policy uncertainty significantly impacts clean energy stock prices. Research by Zhao (2020) demonstrates that endogenous economic policy uncertainty plays a crucial role in influencing the stock returns of clean energy companies, particularly in response to oil price shocks. Moreover, a study by Zeng & Yue (2021) investigates the effect of economic policy uncertainty on renewable and non-renewable energy consumption in the case of BRICS countries, for the period 1991–2019. The results highlight that economic policy uncertainty decreases short-term and long-term firm investment behaviour in clean energy consumption, thereby directly affecting clean energy stock prices.

A substantial body of literature also demonstrates that global stock market volatility significantly impacts clean energy stock prices. Notably, research by Chai et al. (2022) examines the dynamic nonlinear connectedness between green bonds, clean energy stock prices, and global stock prices during the COVID-19. By using a time-varying parameter vector autoregression model (TVP-VAR), the results indicate that an increase in global stock market volatility can lead to a decrease in clean energy stock prices in regions such as the U.S., Europe, and Asia. Furthermore, Liu and Hamori (2020) examine the spillovers of return and volatility transmitted from fossil energies (crude oil and natural gas) and several important financial variables (stock market index, bonds, and the volatility index) to renewable stock markets in the US and Europe. They find that the CBOE Volatility Index (VIX), an index measuring S&P 500 volatility, significantly influences the price direction of renewable energy stocks. Moreover, they highlight that the effect of stock market uncertainty on clean energy stocks is more pronounced in the US than in Europe.

In summary, the impact of features such as macroeconomic variables, economic policy uncertainty, and financial market volatility on the forecasting of clean energy price movements remains significantly understudied. The existing literature primarily discusses the causal relationships but does not sufficiently address the importance of these variables as predictors. This study aims to fill this gap by examining the effects of multiple features, with a particular focus on macroeconomic variables, to better understand how business cycle conditions influence clean energy stock price predictions. This understanding is crucial for investors and policymakers worldwide. For investors, understanding these relationships is crucial to optimise investment strategies in this volatile sector. By forecasting accurately, investors are able to better allocate capital and increase returns on investments by capitalising on economic shifts. For policymakers, this knowledge facilitates informed decision-making regarding energy policy and economic regulation. By understanding how macroeconomic conditions influence clean energy markets, policymakers can craft more effective interventions that stabilise the market and promote sustainable energy development. Accordingly, this study proposes the following hypotheses for further analysis, based on the theoretical frameworks and empirical evidence discussed in this section:

Hypothesis 1 (H1): Among the various machine learning methods applied, ensemble techniques such as Random Forests (RFs) and XGBoost are expected to yield higher predictive accuracy compared to simpler classification methods, such as Naive Bayes.

Hypothesis 2 (H2): The forecasting accuracy of all employed machine learning algorithms will improve with longer forecasting horizons. For instance, a 20-day forecast is expected to demonstrate higher accuracy than a 10-day forecast.

Hypothesis 3 (H3): Among the features analysed, technical indicators will rank as the most important predictors when analysed using SHAP values. Within the non-technical features, economic policy uncertainty and financial market volatility will be identified as the most important. Conversely, inflation is expected to be the least significant macroeconomic feature.

3. Methodology

This section delves into the machine learning techniques utilised for predicting the directional movement of clean energy stock prices, namely Random Forests, XGBoost, Support Vector Machines (SVM), and Naïve Bayes. Furthermore, a detailed description of model specifics is given to elucidate the underlying algorithms, parameter settings, and the rationale behind the selection of these models. The methodological approach utilised in this study is illustrated in Figure 2:

Figure 2: Research Methodology Outline

3.1. Machine Learning Algorithms

3.1.1. Naïve Bayes Classifier

The Naïve Bayes classifier¹ is a type of machine learning algorithm that utilises Bayes' theorem, as shown in Equation (3.1), to perform probabilistic classification tasks. Modeling stock price direction is a classification problem because a binary variable can be used to indicate the direction of stock price change. For the analysis reported in this study,

¹ A classification algorithm, in general, is a function that weighs the input features so that the output separates one class into positive values and the other into negative values. Classifier training is performed to identify the weights (and functions) that provide the most accurate and best separation of the two classes of data (Netoff, 2019).

stock price change from one period to the next can be classified as either positive (“up”) or negative (“down”). The Naïve Bayes classifier operates under the assumption that the features, denoted as x in the equation, are independent given the class label. By analysing the input data corresponding to these features, the Naïve Bayes classifier computes the likelihood of the data being associated with a specific category, labeled as C_j . This approach enables the model to make predictions about the class membership of input instances by estimating the conditional probabilities of the class given the observed feature values, as shown in Figure 3. According to Bayes Theorem:

$$P(C_j|x) = \frac{P(x|C_j) \cdot P(C_j)}{P(x)} \quad (3.1)$$

where C_j is the number of classes and x is the feature vector. $P(C_j|x)$ denotes the posterior probability of the class C_j , given the predictor (feature). $P(x|C_j)$ represents the likelihood, which is the probability of predictor given class C_j . $P(C_j)$ is the prior probability of class C_j occurring independently of x . $P(x)$ is the prior probability of predictor x .

Given a feature vector, x , the Naïve Bayes classifier predicts the class $\hat{C}$ that maximises the posterior probability $P(C_j|X)$. The “Naïve” aspect of this algorithm stems from the assumption mentioned before, that all predictors (or features) in the dataset are mutually independent (James et al., 2013). Given this assumption and the fact that $P(x)$ is constant for all classes, the prediction is simplified to:

$$\hat{C} = \arg \max_C P(C) \prod_{i=1}^n P(x_i|C) \quad (3.2)$$

Simply, the classifier calculates the product of the individual feature probabilities for each class, multiplies it by the prior probability of the class, and selects the class with the highest value.

Incorporating Naive Bayes for stock price prediction involves balancing its computational simplicity and efficacy in handling categorical data against the drawbacks of its independence assumption and potential inaccuracies in sparse datasets. Academic discussions, such as those by Zhang and Zhou (2004) in their exploration of Naive Bayes in text categorisation, highlight these strengths and weaknesses, which are crucial when considering the complex, interdependent nature of financial markets.

Figure 3: An example of Naïve Bayes

3.1.2. Random Forest

The Random Forest algorithm, an ensemble technique, trains multiple decision trees through bootstrapping and combines their outcomes using aggregation, a process known as bagging. By definition, an ensemble method combines multiple models, such as decision trees, to create a more powerful and accurate meta-model (Zhang & Ma, 2012).

A key aspect of single decision tree models is their capability to achieve high predictive accuracy when applied to training datasets; however, they are prone to high variance. High variance poses a challenge as small variations in the dataset can lead to instability in the model's performance. This issue can be mitigated through the application of ensemble methods (such as in the Random Forest), which generate multiple, less correlated decision trees to consolidate their predictions. This algorithm characteristic increases prediction consistency and reliability (Breiman, 2001). Additionally, bootstrapping refers to the technique of training multiple distinct decision trees simultaneously on diverse subsets of the training data, each utilising different feature selections. This approach guarantees the uniqueness of each tree within the Random Forest, effectively decreasing the classifier's aggregate variance and enhancing its robustness. For the final decision, the Random Forest algorithm selects a random subset of features from the complete set of predictors for each split within a tree. This stochastic selection of features leads to a minimisation of correlation among individual trees (James et al., 2013). The final prediction is then derived by averaging the predictions from all trees, resulting in a consolidated and more accurate prediction. This process is shown in Figure 4.

Critically, although the Random Forest classifier offers improved accuracy and robustness, especially with complex datasets, the algorithm suffers from several disadvantages. First, the algorithm requires significant computational power and resources, as

it involves building and combining numerous trees. This also means that the training process can be time-consuming (James et al., 2013). Secondly, the ensemble nature of Random Forest makes it less interpretable compared to a single decision tree, making it challenging to understand the significance of each variable in the model (Hastie et al, 2009). Lastly, while Random Forest performs well with a large number of features, it can exhibit bias towards features with more levels or categories, potentially affecting model fairness and accuracy (Hastie et al, 2009).

Figure 4: Random Forest Bagging Example

3.1.3. Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost)

Extreme gradient boosting, also known as XGBoost (Chen & Guestrin, 2016), is another type of ensemble model. Gradient Boosting Tree models employ decision trees as base learners, which are individually weak but collectively form a strong predictive model. The basis of Gradient Boosting lies in its iterative refinement of predictions. It begins by making an initial prediction for the target values and calculates the residuals, which are the differences between these predictions and the actual target values. In subsequent steps, the algorithm focuses on these residuals, effectively trying to predict the error of the previous prediction.

With each iteration, a new decision tree is constructed to address the residuals left by the previous trees. This process involves mapping the features that are less effective in making accurate predictions (the weak features) to the current residuals, thereby gradually leading the predictions closer to the true target values. This iterative correction continues until the model reaches a predetermined number of trees or the improvement in prediction becomes negligible. Unlike the Random Forest approach, which builds trees in parallel and combines their predictions at the end, Gradient Boosting builds one tree at a time. Each new tree in the sequence corrects the errors made by the preceding trees, making this approach inherently sequential.

The “Extreme” stems from the use of a second-order approximation (or the “curvature”) of the loss function, into the optimisation (James et al., 2013). Typically, gradient boosting algorithms improve model predictions by minimising a loss function, which quantifies the difference between the predicted and actual outcomes. By considering the curvature, XGBoost can better understand the loss function's landscape, leading to more accurate and efficient updates during the learning process.

The process of using a XGBoost can be illustrated in Figure 5:

Figure 5: The Extreme Gradient Boosting Process

In the Figure 5, α_i and r_i represents the regularisation parameters and residuals computed with the i^{th} tree respectively, and h_i is a function that is trained to predict

residuals, r_i , using X for the i^{th} tree. To compute α_i , the algorithm uses the residuals computed r_i and computes the following:

$$\arg \min_{\alpha} = \sum_{i=1}^m L(Y_i, F_{i-1}(X_i) + \alpha h_i(X_i, r_{i-1}))$$

Where, $L(Y, F(X))$ is the differentiable loss function.

Overall, XGBoost is advantageous for its performance and speed in machine learning operations, partly due to its use of a second-order approximation to the loss function which allows for more accurate model updates. However, it's not without drawbacks; for instance, XGBoost involves a considerable number of manually specified hyperparameters, a tuning process that can be complex and time-consuming (Nam et al., 2021).

3.1.4. Support Vector Machine (SVM)

Support Vector Machines (SVMs) are a class of supervised learning algorithms that can be employed for classification and is the most widely used machine learning technique-based pattern classification (Hsu et al., 2003). In the context of predicting stock prices, SVMs can be particularly effective due to their ability to model non-linear relationships and their robustness against overfitting in high-dimensional spaces, which is often the case with financial data. The process of applying SVMs for stock price prediction is shown in Figure 6.

SVM works by constructing a hyper-plane (a decision boundary that separates different classes of data points) in a high-dimensional feature space of the input data (Cortes & Vapnik, 1995). Then the algorithm uses the hyperplane (represented as H_1 and H_2) to enforce a linear separation of input samples, which belong to different classes (represented by Class X and Class Y). The samples that that lie on boundaries of different classes are referred to as support vectors. For complex problems, such as stock price prediction, the support vectors can be located using advanced vector geometry. The underlying principle behind SVM-based classification is to maximise the margin hyperplane (MMH) between the support vectors using kernel functions (a mathematical function that transforms data into a high-dimensional space to facilitate linear separation). Data is mapped to a higher-dimensional space in order to linearise non-linear relationships observed in a specific dimension.

In the context of stock price prediction, SVM uses historical stock price data as input vectors in the feature space. By employing an SVM with a suitable kernel function, the input data is mapped to a higher-dimensional space where these complex market dynamics can be more easily separated linearly, allowing for more accurate predictions of stock price movements based on past trends.

Figure 6: Support Vector Machine (SVM) Process

Support Vector Machines (SVMs) offer significant advantages for financial market analysis, particularly due to their efficient training process and adaptability to high-dimensional datasets. However, interpreting SVM models can be complex unless the features are inherently understandable, and their non-parametric methodology may lead to ambiguous results (Mohamed, 2017; Jakkula, 2006; Auria & Moro, 2008).

3.2. Setup of the Models

In this study, a comparison and an accuracy evaluation are made on the selected machine learning algorithms. The methodology and algorithm architecture presented in this study have been refined and enhanced based on the frameworks proposed in Sadorsky's (2022a & 2022b) research articles.

In accordance with standard machine learning practices, the dataset was split into two subsets: 70% was allocated for training purposes, while the remaining 30% was reserved for

model evaluation and testing. For each predictive model, multi-step forecasts ranging from a one-day to a twenty-day horizon were generated. This forecasting timeframe offers a deeper insight into the variation of model precision over increasing forecast lengths. The twenty-day maximum was selected to reflect the typical number of trading days in a standard month (Sadorsky, 2022b). In the classification tasks within the paper, the confusion matrix serves as the foundation for deriving predictive accuracy metrics. The accuracy score, computed as the sum of true positives and true negatives over the number of all predictions, quantifies model performance on a scale from zero to one, with one indicating a ‘perfect’ fit (Table 1²).

Table 1: Confusion Matrix Analysis

Confusion Matrix		Predicted (Target)			
		Positive	Negative		
Actual (Model)	Positive	True Positive (a)	False Negative (b)	<i>Positive Predicted Value</i>	$\frac{a}{(a + b)}$
	Negative	False Positive (c)	True Negative (d)	<i>Negative Predicted Value</i>	$\frac{d}{(c + d)}$
		<i>Sensitivity</i>	<i>Specificity</i>	Accuracy = $\frac{(a+d)}{(a+b+c+d)}$	
		$\frac{a}{(a + c)}$	$\frac{d}{(b + d)}$		

To enhance the robustness of the findings and provide more comprehensive insights beyond the simplistic accuracy metric, this study incorporates two additional classification metrics. Initially, the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) Curve is utilised to illustrate the balance between sensitivity (true positive rate) and specificity (1 - false positive rate). An ideal model's ROC curve closely follows the left-hand border and then ascends towards the top border of the ROC space, denoting high accuracy (James et al., 2013). A curve that gravitates towards the 45-degree diagonal of the ROC space signals weak accuracy, mirroring the performance of a random classifier (James et al., 2013). This curve is used to calculate the Area Under the Curve (AUC), which quantifies the overall ability of the model to discriminate between positive and negative classes. The higher the AUC, the better the model is at correctly classifying outcomes (Hanley & McNeil, 1982).

² **Sensitivity/Recall** is the proportion of actual positive cases which are correctly identified. **Specificity** is the proportion of actual negative cases which are correctly identified. **Positive Predictive Value/Precision** is the proportion of positive cases that were correctly identified. **Negative Predictive Value** is the proportion of negative cases that were correctly identified.

Subsequently, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) statistic is employed to quantify the model's capacity to discriminate between classes (Chakravart, Laha, and Roy, 1967). This statistic captures the maximal divergence between the cumulative distribution functions (CDFs) of positive and negative classes. A higher K-S value suggests high discriminative power, and thus a pronounced separation between the class distributions. The K-S statistic spans from 0 to 1, with values approaching 1 indicating a model's strong ability to distinguish between the two classes, such as positive and negative trading days in our context.

In calculating feature importance, SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) values, originating from cooperative game theory, offer a method for quantifying the contribution of individual features to the predictive model's output (Siemers & Bajorath, 2023; Främling et al., 2021; Kumar & Chandran, 2021). Each feature's value is calculated by assessing the change in prediction accuracy that results from adding that feature to all combinations of other features. This approach, detailed by Lundberg & Lee (2017), ensures a fair distribution of importance across features, based on their marginal contribution to the model's performance. While Shapley values provide a theoretically complete and consistent measure of feature importance, they require significant computational resources, which can lead to longer processing times compared to other methods like permutation importance (Colini-Baldeschi et al., 2017).

All calculations were done in R using the `e1071` package (Meyer et al., 2021), the `caret` package (Kuhn et al., 2020), the `metrics` package (Hamner et al., 2021), the `quantmod` package (Ryan, 2008), and the `tidyquant` package (Dancho & Vaughan, 2023).

4. Data

The study's dataset comprised prices of clean energy ETFs, including PBD, PBW, QCLN, and ICLN, along with macroeconomic variables: the 10-Year US Government Bond Yield, Economic Policy Uncertainty Index, US Citigroup Economic Surprise Index, CBOE Volatility Index, DBCVIX USD Volatility Index, S&P GSCI Commodity Index, and the US Consumer Price Index. The study is based on a period of fifteen years extending from November 3rd 2008 to November 3rd 2023. Starting from 2008 allows to examine the behaviour of varying systematic risks of the investment in clean energy stocks, especially during the three major crises: the great recession in 2008, the COVID-19 pandemic, and the European energy crisis. All data was retrieved from a Bloomberg Terminal.

Clean energy stock prices are measured using the four most widely traded clean energy exchange traded funds (ETFs): Invesco Global Clean Energy ETF (PBD), Invesco WilderHill Clean Energy ETF (PBW), First Trust NASDAQ Clean Edge Green Energy ETF (QCLN), iShares Global Clean Energy ETF (ICLN). Table 2 offers a comparison of each ETF used:

Table 2: Comparison of Each Clean Energy ETF Used in Analysis (Source: Bloomberg)

ETF Name	Geographical Focus	Number of Holdings	Assets Under Management (AUM)	Holdings Examples
PBD	Global	111	\$141.30 Million	Shihlin Electric & Engineering, Toyo Tanso Co Ltd, Chung-Hsin Electric & Machiner
PBW	United States	73	\$441.19 Million	NEXTracker Inc, American Superconductor Group, Solid Power Inc
QCLN	United States	57	\$997.30 Million	ON Semiconductor Corp, First Solar Inc, Albemarle Corp
ICLN	Global	102	\$2.691 Billion	Enphase Energy Inc, First Solar Inc, Vestas Wind Systems A/S

Alameer et al. (2020) emphasize the importance of selecting appropriate input variables (features) for the development of precise prediction models. Table 3 offers a brief description of the seven selected feature variables used:

Table 3: Descriptions of Macroeconomic Features

Feature Name	General Description
10-Year US Government Bond Yield	<p>The dataset of the 10-Year US Government Bond Yield contains an extensive historical archive of yield figures for United States Treasury bonds, notable by their ten-year maturity horizon. The yield dynamics of these sovereign debt instruments are affected by many macroeconomic influences, such as the strategic monetary policy, current and expected inflationary pressures, as well as the broader spectrum of global economic health.</p>
Global Economic Policy Uncertainty Index	<p>The Global Economic Policy Uncertainty Index (Baker et al., 2016) is constructed through a methodological approach that employs keyword searches across various news and media outlets. This index quantifies the degree of uncertainty pertaining to economic policy on a global scale.</p>
United States Citigroup Economic Surprise Index	<p>A sophisticated tool that measures the degree to which actual economic indicators diverge from market expectations. Developed by Citigroup, the index is calculated by comparing real economic data against consensus forecasts. This index serves as a barometer for the current economic sentiment, capturing the surprises in economic data releases that can significantly impact financial markets (Clements & Galvão, 2017).</p>
CBOE Volatility Index	<p>The CBOE Volatility Index, commonly referred to as the VIX or the “Fear Index”, is a real-time market index representing the market's expectations for volatility over the next 30 days. Introduced by the Chicago Board Options Exchange (CBOE), the VIX is derived from the price inputs of S&P 500 index options and is designed to reflect investors' consensus view of future (30-day) expected stock market volatility.</p>
DBCX USD Volatility Index	<p>Deutsche Bank's CVIX, serves as a daily indicator of volatility within the foreign exchange (FX) market. It is designed to capture the intensity and frequency of fluctuations in currency values, highlighting the potential for shifts in volatility levels. Furthermore, it serves as a barometer for underlying economic, political, and geopolitical events that can influence currency markets.</p>
S&P GSCI Commodity Index	<p>The S&P GSCI (Standard & Poor's Goldman Sachs Commodity Index) is an aggregate, benchmark index that measures the performance of the commodity market. It encompasses a broad spectrum of commodity futures contracts, representing various sectors, including but not limited to energy products, agricultural goods, industrial metals, and precious metals.</p>
US Consumer Price Index	<p>The US Consumer Price Index (CPI) is a crucial economic indicator that measures the average change over time in the prices paid by urban consumers for a market basket of consumer goods and services. Administered by the Bureau of Labor Statistics (BLS), the CPI is widely used to measure inflationary trends within the United States economy.</p>

In constructing technical indicators for stock price prediction, this study employs a set of widely recognized indicators including the 50-day and 200-day moving averages, Williams' Accumulation/Distribution (WAD), Stochastic Oscillators (StoFASTK), Moving Average Convergence Divergence (MACD), On Balance Volume, and the Relative Strength Index (RSI). These indicators have been validated by a body of research for their utility in forecasting stock price movements (Bustos & Pomares-Quimbaya, 2020; Htun et al., 2023; Chandola et al., 2022; Sonkavde et al., 2023; Yang et al., 2022). The calculations for these indicators were performed using the default settings provided by the R package TTR (Ulrich, 2020).

The time series pattern for the four ETFs - PBD, PBW, QCLN, and ICLN - as illustrated in Figure 7, along with the seven selected features showcased in Figure 8, are discussed herein. The analysis reveals a generally stable trend in clean energy stock prices from January 2, 2013, to January 2, 2019, with the notable exception of 2014. 2014 was marked by significant increases in clean energy investment and reflected strong performances in many of the main regions for clean energy deployment, with China up 32% to a record \$89.5bn, the US up 8% to \$51.8bn (its highest figure since 2012), and Japan up 12% to \$41.3bn (BloombergNEF, 2015). Post-January 2019, there was a notable rise in clean energy stock prices, reaching a peak in early January 2021, coinciding with the start of the COVID-19 pandemic. Explanations for this trend revolve around the unprecedented levels of fiscal stimulus by governments worldwide, and more aggressive climate targets and policies such as the European Union Green Deal and the US Inflation Reduction Act. Furthermore, an accelerated adoption of various technological advancements and shifted consumer preferences towards more sustainable services also caused this upward trend (Sadorsky, 2022b). Since 2021, prices experienced a pronounced downturn, with price valuations retracting to levels last seen in 2019. As the world emerged from the COVID-19 pandemic into the global energy crisis, the economy was characterised by an environment of higher interest rates (outside China) and high inflationary pressures. Financing projects became more challenging, and companies' profitability were impacted due to a heightened dependence on a higher cost of equity financing and elevated input costs of key raw materials, including critical minerals. Clean energy investments, known for having a high initial expense offset by lower ongoing operating costs, are particularly sensitive to increases in borrowing rates compared to other energy investments (IEA, 2023).

Figure 7: Time Series Plot of Clean Energy ETFs

Figure 8: Time Series of Features (Macroeconomic Variables, Economic Policy Uncertainty, and Financial Market Volatility)

The summary statistics presented in Table 5 suggest that PBD and QCLN exhibit a more favorable risk-return profile when compared to PBW and ICLN, as evidenced by their lower coefficient of variation. Among the feature data, the CESIUSD and GSCPI_Index have the most variation and US CPI is the least variable. All data display non-normality as for each variable skewness and kurtosis are present, and the null hypothesis of normality are rejected (normtest.p).

Table 5: Summary Statistics

	median	mean	std.dev	coef.var	skewness	kurtosis	normtes	normtest.p
PBD	0.0810	0.0192	1.8155	94.6724	-0.3420	7.9590	0.9252	0.0000
PBW	0.0000	0.0088	2.2932	262.0158	-0.1283	4.0459	0.9552	0.0000
QCLN	0.1181	0.0489	2.1381	43.7609	-0.0731	3.7546	0.9586	0.0000
ICLN	0.0000	0.0046	1.9996	432.9703	-0.1197	9.0355	0.9084	0.0000
USGG10YR	2.3732	2.4253	0.8398	0.3463	0.1518	-0.1951	0.9913	0.0000
EPU_Index	98.2900	113.8216	67.3217	0.5915	1.6894	5.0432	0.8809	0.0000
CESIUSD	5.1000	7.0992	51.6068	7.2694	0.9987	4.1542	0.9320	0.0000
VIX	17.4600	19.7951	8.6095	0.4349	2.2137	7.5806	0.8143	0.0000
DBCPIX	8.9900	9.5173	3.0166	0.3170	1.4698	3.2971	0.8956	0.0000
GSCPI_Index	0.0400	0.3090	1.1963	3.8718	1.3386	1.4861	0.8674	0.0000
CPI_US	239.5570	246.6861	24.6456	0.0999	0.08985	0.0976	0.9134	0.0000

Note: PBD, PBW, QCLN and ICLN are all expressed in continuous compounded returns. Data for the period November 3, 2008, to November 3, 2023 (3777 daily observations).

Figure 9 provides a visual representation of the correlations among the variables of interest. The correlation coefficients indicate a strong relationship between the ETFs under study, with values ranging from 0.8 to 0.9. Additionally, the US Consumer Price Index (CPI) shows a substantial correlation with the First Trust NASDAQ Clean Edge Green Energy ETF (QCLN), with a coefficient in the range of 0.7 to 0.8. The GSCPI Index also demonstrates notable correlations with all the ETFs, with coefficients ranging from 0.6 to 0.7. Figure 10 employs a chord diagram to illustrate the dynamic interconnectedness within the market. The circle consists of 11 variables, with the arc length of each segment corresponding to a specific feature. The width of each chord indicates the strength of the interaction between variables. Percentages along the outer circumference denote the share attributed to each variable. This visual representation reinforces the relationships detailed in the correlation matrix.

Figure 9: Correlation Matrix

Figure 10: Chord Diagram

Lastly, Figure 11 showcases the proportion of up (positive) days for each forecasted day across various clean energy ETFs. The values, which fluctuate between 0.5 and 0.55, suggest a relatively balanced distribution of positive days.

Figure 11: The Percentage of Positive Days

5. Empirical Results

5.1. General Performance of the Models

This section offers an in-depth analysis of the forecasting performance of the machine learning models used in the paper. Building on the methodologies outlined in Section 3.2, the paper employs three distinct measures of accuracy to evaluate the models' performance: the Accuracy metric; the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve; and the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) statistic. Each of these metrics provides unique insights into model performance, allowing for a detailed assessment across different dimensions of accuracy.

Figure 12 and Table 6 display the classification performance as measured by the standard classification Accuracy metric, from which several observations can be deduced. Firstly, models such as Random Forests (RF), XGBoost, and Support Vector Machine (SVM) demonstrate higher prediction accuracy across all four ETF datasets when compared to Naïve Bayes (NB) models. This disparity in performance can be attributed to several factors inherent to the design and functioning of these algorithms, such as being able to handle the non-linearity and feature interactions, typical of stock market data. This reveals that advanced ensemble machine learning models display greater accuracy over conventional classification techniques. Secondly, among all the models and across all datasets, the RF exhibits the highest predictive accuracy, obtaining an average result of 92.3% (at a 20-day forecast horizon). The RF model was followed by the XGBoost, SVM, and NB model respectively. Notably, after a 10-day forecasting period, both RF and XGBoost models demonstrate robust performance, with accuracies near or exceeding 70%. Specifically, in the 10-day forecast for QCLN, RF and XGBoost show remarkable accuracies of 84.6% and 82.5%, respectively. Extending the horizon to between 15 and 20 days, RF and XGBoost models demonstrate robust predictive performance, often exceeding 80% accuracy. Notably, in the case of the QCLN dataset, the accuracy surpasses 90% for both models. In contrast, during this same forecast period, SVM peaks at an accuracy range of 73-75%, while Naïve Bayes lags behind with 55-60% accuracy. Thirdly, it is worth highlighting a specific trend: in the very short term, spanning 0-3 days, SVM outperforms all other models in predictive accuracy. This suggests that SVM may be particularly adept at capturing patterns over brief intervals, which is crucial for short-term trading strategies.

Figure 12: (a) Accuracy values for PBW, (b) Accuracy values for PBD, (c) Accuracy values for QCLN, (d) Accuracy values for ICLN

(c)

(d)

Table 6: Comparative Analysis of the Accuracy Metric for 10-day versus 20-day Forecasting Horizons

	10-day	20-day
PBW		
RF	0.8431	0.9459
XGBoost	0.7235	0.8379
SVM	0.7497	0.7501
NB	0.5993	0.5975
PBD		
RF	0.8265	0.8754
XGBoost	0.6927	0.7893
SVM	0.7256	0.7462
NB	0.5893	0.5903
QCLN		
RF	0.8458	0.9501
XGBoost	0.8249	0.9347
SVM	0.7455	0.7502
NB	0.5753	0.5790
ICLN		
RF	0.8481	0.9201
XGBoost	0.6899	0.8294
SVM	0.7212	0.7477
NB	0.5699	0.5821

According to Ben Jabeur et al. (2020), the AUC (Area under the Curve) indicator is a common metric for assessing a model's overall discriminatory power. In the analysis undertaken by this study, relying solely on the classification Accuracy metric can lead to misleading interpretations due to the prevalence of imbalanced datasets (Luque et al., 2019). An illustrative case is the prediction of stock prices in a long-term "bullish" market, where a model might show high accuracy simply by predicting a rise consistently. This apparent precision does not necessarily equate to true predictive capability since the model could be capitalising on the dataset's skew rather than capturing the underlying patterns that drive market movements. Thus, the AUC indicator is a more flexible performance metric; and

calculated from the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve (Mai et al., 2019) shown in Figure 13. Importantly, based on the Accuracy metric, the Random Forest model emerges as the most precise in terms of predictive capability. Given this general finding, the focus will now shift exclusively to further examination of the accuracy of the Random Forest model to thoroughly understand its performance in predictive tasks across the datasets.

The initial observation from Figure 13 is that the ROC curve for the PBW and PBD Random Forest Model (top row) are very close to the top left corner, indicating a very high true positive rate (sensitivity) and a low false positive rate (1- specificity). This suggests that the model has excellent performance in distinguishing between the positive and negative classes. For QCLN and ICLN datasets the ROC curve starts off well by being close to the left-hand side but then plateaus quickly. This suggests that increases in sensitivity are achieved with very few false positives initially, but beyond a certain point, there are diminishing returns in sensitivity for any reduction in specificity. The accuracy of this model is satisfactory; however, it does not reach the level of precision demonstrated by the PBW and PBD models.

Table 7 summarises the AUC over a 10-day and 20-day forecast horizon. We first note that the AUC values at both 10-day and 20-day are consistently above 0.8. The AUC ranges from 82.7% to 84.8% at the 10-day horizon, and from 87.5% to 95% at the 20-day horizon. This demonstrates that ensemble machine learning models such as Random Forest increase model efficiency when the forecast horizon is higher. Moreover, a part of these results was attributed to the new models' potential to substantially minimise type-I errors, relative to standard ones, while the horizon is rising (Nti et al., 2020). This reinforces the result that Random Forest algorithms provide robust predictive power for financial institutions and stakeholders in the energy transition sectors.

Table 7: Comparison of AUC Metric Across Datasets for 10-Day and 20-Day Forecasting Horizons

	10-day	20-day
PBW	0.8431	0.9459
PBD	0.8265	0.8754
QCLN	0.8458	0.9501
ICLN	0.8481	0.9201

Figure 13: Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) Curve Plots for (a) PBW, (b) PBD, (c) QCLN, (d) ICLN

Proceeding to the third accuracy assessment, the focus will now shift to examining the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) statistic to provide a definitive synthesis of the findings from the previous two accuracy metric evaluations. As mentioned in Section 3.2, the K-S statistic quantifies the maximum distance between the cumulative distribution functions (CDFs) of the two groups. A high K-S value indicates a better discriminatory power of the model, meaning the model is more capable of distinguishing between the positive and negative classes, the primary objective of the stock price binary classification problem. Figure 14 shows the plot and statistic value of each class's CDF where the “good” class indicates the positive trading class and “bad”, the negative trading class.

Employing a Random Forest model across the datasets yields K-S statistics ranging from 0.2616 to 0.2907, with QCLN exhibiting the highest discriminatory capability and ICLN the lowest, albeit the difference is marginal. These figures suggest a moderate level of discriminative power, capable of distinguishing between positive and negative instances to a certain extent. However, there remains room for enhancement to increase these statistics and

thus improve model performance. Nonetheless, interpreting these results without considering the context of stock market analysis would be incomplete. Given the clean energy stock market's inherent volatility and the myriad factors affecting prediction accuracy such as regulatory shifts and fluctuating energy prices, a model that surpasses any chance in its predictions offers a considerable advantage to investors. This degree of discrimination indicates that the model has identified patterns or trends not readily apparent to the average investor. Moreover, determining the probability of positive versus negative trading days is crucial for effective risk management and decision-making, enabling the development of strategies that reduce losses and maximise gains. Notably, the model's ability to detect scenarios more likely to yield positive returns can significantly aid investors in timing their market entry and exit, and thus improve investment strategies.

Figure 14: Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) Test Plots Across Datasets for (a) PBW, (b) PBD, (c) QCLN, (d) ICLN

5.2. Variable Importance

In the objective of forecasting clean energy stock prices, understanding the relative impact of each variable on the prediction outcome is crucial. This research employs SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) values to analyse the contribution of various factors to the predictive model. Figures 15 to 18 illustrate the importance of 14 technical and non-technical features across four datasets, presenting two distinct visualisations for each: the Beeswarm plot and the Mean Absolute Shapley Value plot. It is essential to recognise that the Beeswarm plot is arranged to showcase the most influential features at the top, descending in order of significance. Although the feature ranking is consistent across both plot types in each figure, the Beeswarm plot offers an added dimension by showing the relationship between a feature's value and its importance in prediction. This plot employs a colour-coded scheme to intuitively convey the following: higher values of a feature are represented with warmer colours, while lower values are indicated by cooler colours.

Focusing primarily on the Mean Absolute Shapley Value illustrated in plot (a) of each figure, the horizontal axis represents the probability of being categorised into the positive classification within the binary class framework. Across the four datasets examined, a consistent pattern emerges, highlighting the Relative Strength Index (RSI) and the Moving Average Convergence/Divergence (MACD) as the most important technical indicators. On average, the RSI is found to increase the likelihood of a positive classification by 26%, while the MACD contributes to a 15.7% increase across the datasets. This finding aligns with existing empirical research, notably a study by Chong et al. (2014), which demonstrated the capacity of both RSI and MACD strategies to generate significant abnormal returns in stock markets of various OECD countries, including the London Stock Exchange. This evidence not only reaffirms the efficacy of these indicators in diverse developed markets but also signals strong investor confidence in them. In contrast, the least important features identified across the datasets include the Moving Average (MA) and the Williams' Accumulation/Distribution (WAD) indicator. Specifically, the WAD indicator increases the probability of a positive classification by a mere 0.8% for PBW, whereas the MA200 does so by only 0.6% for QCLN.

Regarding non-technical features, namely economic variables, the analysis reveals distinct patterns across different datasets. For PBW, the Economic Policy Uncertainty Index (EPU), CBOE Volatility Index (VIX), and Citigroup Economic Surprise Index for the United States (CESIUSD) stand out as pivotal economic indicators. These indicators respectively

increase the probability of a positive classification by an average of 1.75%, 1.5%, and 1.3%. In the datasets for PBD and QCLN, the EPU, VIX, and the United States 10-Year Bond Yield (USGG10YR) emerge as the most important, with PBD experiencing an average increase in the probability of positive classification by 1.25%, 1.2%, and 1.05% for each indicator respectively. For QCLN, these increases are slightly higher, at 1.35%, 1.25%, and 1.2% respectively. For the ICLN dataset, the most important features are identified as the EPU, the Deutsche Bank Foreign Exchange Volatility Index (DBCXVIX), and the VIX, enhancing the probability of a positive outcome by 1.8%, 1.53%, and 1.25% respectively. In contrast, the Goldman Sachs Commodity Index (GSCI) is noted as the least impactful non-technical indicator across all four datasets, with a marginal average increase in positive classification probability of 0.62%.

The Beeswarm plot, identified as plot b of each figure, not only reinforces the ranking of features by importance but also allows for a deeper examination of how the value of a feature impacts its importance. In these plots, positive SHAP values signify a feature's positive influence on the predictive outcome, whereas negative SHAP values indicate a negative effect. Consistently across all datasets, higher RSI values are associated with increased importance, as indicated by the clustering of warmer-coloured data points on the positive side of the SHAP value horizontal axis. Conversely, for the MACD indicator, lower values tend to be more significant. Specifically, in the datasets for PBW and QCLN, the MA50, MA200, and WAD indicators show that higher values correspond to greater importance. However, an inverse relationship is observed for QCLN concerning these three indicators, highlighting a distinct pattern of importance. For PBD, it's noted that higher WAD values and lower values for both MA50 and MA200 are more crucial. Across the datasets for PBD, PBW, ICLN, and QCLN, lower values of the EPU are deemed more important, while higher values of the VIX indicate greater significance.

Figure 15: PBW (a) Mean Absolute Shapley Value Plot, (b) Beeswarm SHAP Plot

Figure 16: PBD (a) Mean Absolute Shapley Value Plot, (b) Beeswarm SHAP Plot

Figure 17: QCLN (a) Mean Absolute Shapley Value Plot, (b) Beeswarm SHAP Plot

Figure 18: ICLN (a) Mean Absolute Shapley Value Plot, (b) Beeswarm SHAP Plot

5.3. Discussion

The analysis of this study offers several interesting results and insights. First, the results indicate that ensemble methods, specifically Random Forest and XGBoost, outperform Support Vector Machine and Naive Bayes in terms of predictive accuracy. At a five-day forecast horizon, both Random Forest and XGBoost achieve accuracy rates between 66% and 75%. Remarkably, after a 15-day horizon, Random Forest reaches a performance of over 87% and reaches up to 95% in predicting the performance of the NASDAQ Clean Edge Green Energy (QCLN) ETF. These findings are important in showing the superior predictive accuracy of ensemble machine learning methods over simpler classification techniques, a result that is well-supported in the existing literature (Hu et al., 2022; Ming et al., 2022). This confirms that Hypotheses 1 and 2 are supported by the findings in this study. An important point to raise is that this result challenges the Efficient Markets Hypothesis (EMH). The EMH is a fundamental concept in finance that posits that asset prices reflect all available information, and therefore follow a random walk (Fama, 1970). If the Efficient Markets Hypothesis were fully applicable, the consistently high accuracy of these models would not be possible, as stock price movements would be entirely unpredictable and not subject to forecasting based on historical data and feature data. This contradiction suggests that market inefficiencies do exist, allowing these advanced models to capture patterns not detailed in traditional financial analysis.

Second, this study proves that technical indicators are significant predictors of clean energy stock price directions, outperforming macroeconomic variables. This finding aligns with the current research indicating that technical indicators are crucial for accurate clean

energy stock price forecasting (Sadorsky, 2022a; Sadorsky, 2022b). Notably, the RSI and MACD are the most important features for predicting clean energy stock prices.

Third, among the non-technical indicators, EPU and VIX are the most important. The VIX, which quantifies the market's expectation of volatility in the S&P 500, plays a key role in forecasting clean energy ETFs. This importance of the VIX is not surprising, considering that market volatility can significantly influence asset prices. There are two main mechanisms through which market volatility affects clean energy stock prices: an increase in the risk premium (Batten et al., 2016) and higher discount rates (Chen et al., 2023). Increased market volatility can lead investors to demand a higher risk premium when financing clean energy projects. The increase in the cost of capital of clean energy investments can lead to higher costs for developing these projects and lower prices for their assets. Financial market volatility could also lead to higher discount rates of clean energy investments. Higher discount rates reduce the present value of future cash flows. Consequently, clean energy projects become less attractive to investors, who may seek higher returns to compensate for the heightened risk associated with market volatility.

Among all economic indicators, it is notably unexpected that the EPU Index results as the most important non-technical feature influencing stock performance across all datasets examined. However, clean energy sectors are particularly sensitive to energy policy changes, regulations, and governmental support, making the EPU a critical indicator (Drago & Gatto, 2022). High EPU levels signal increased uncertainty regarding future economic policies, potentially leading to reduced investments and volatile stock prices in clean energy. Investors might perceive higher risks in periods of elevated EPU, prompting shifts in asset allocations. Specifically, for QCLN, its portfolio structure - where 56% of its total assets are concentrated in the top 10 performing stocks, predominantly U.S. companies - increases its vulnerability to shifts in economic policy uncertainty.

Fourth, the analysis reveals a crucial insight into the interaction between clean energy ETFs and the United States 10-Year Bond Yield (USGG10YR). The QCLN and Invesco Global Clean Energy (PBD) ETFs show increased sensitivity to shifts in the USGG10YR, whereas PBW and ICLN show weak sensitivity to the USGG10YR. This differential in sensitivity can be understood through several lenses. Firstly, both QCLN and PBD are large and mid-cap companies which are particularly vulnerable to shifts in U.S. interest rates. Higher bond yields, signalling rising interest rates, could elevate operational and expansion project financing costs for these companies, directly impacting their market valuation and the

ETFs' performance. Furthermore, given QCLN's investment focus on U.S.-based clean energy companies, which rely on direct financing for growth and operations, fluctuations in US interest rates affect their borrowing costs directly. It is important to note that the Invesco WilderHill Clean Energy ETF prioritises small-cap and growth-centric companies within the clean energy sector. Such companies are often driven more by innovation, market demand for green solutions, and regulatory incentives rather than the direct influence of macroeconomic variable fluctuations like interest rates. The intrinsic growth potential of these firms is considered to outweigh the potential drawbacks of rising capital costs due to higher interest rates.

Fifth, another crucial result for discussion is the weak importance of US inflation, indicated by the Consumer Price Index (CPI_US). CPI_US holds limited importance in predictive models, as indicated by an absolute mean SHAP value of 0.45% across all four datasets (Figures 15 to 18). The decreased importance of inflation indicates that these stocks may not serve as effective inflation hedges. Historically, the adoption of clean energy faced significant challenges due to its perceived high capital and operating expenditures (Sovacool & Dworkin, 2015). However, this narrative has shifted over the past two decades. The levelized cost of clean energy (LCOE) for sources such as solar and onshore wind has seen a strong decline since 2009, making these alternatives more cost-effective than coal. Lazard's annual LCOE analysis highlights this transformation, illustrating a dramatic reduction in costs. For instance, the mean LCOE for Solar Photovoltaic (PV) technology was \$359 per megawatt-hour (MWh) in 2009, decreasing to \$60 per MWh by 2023 - representing a decline of over 142% (Lazard, 2023). This cost efficiency likely safeguards clean energy investments from inflation-driven market shifts, limiting CPI_US's predictive importance. Furthermore, the direct impact of inflation on equities can vary depending on the time horizon considered (Zhang, 2021). In the short term, abrupt increases in inflation may result in volatility within financial markets. However, companies in this sector are better positioned to pass on cost increases to consumers or capitalise on inflationary periods in the longer term due to the increased demand for clean energy solutions.

Following the analysis and discussion presented, it is reasonable to confirm that Hypotheses 1, 2, and 3 have been empirically validated.

6. Concluding Remarks and Practical Implications

Climate change represents an unprecedented challenge to global stability and growth, necessitating an urgent shift away from conventional fossil fuels to alternative, renewable forms of energy. As nations worldwide navigate towards low-carbon economic frameworks, the importance of clean energy is becoming more pronounced. This development has made clean energy equities a significantly attractive investment, where stakeholders are motivated by the dual prospects of financial returns and an alignment of environmentally conscious objectives. However, despite the need for precise forecasting and knowledge of predictor importance, there is a surprising absence of research focused on the forecasting of clean energy stock prices. This study aims to fill this gap by exploring the influence of fundamental macroeconomic variables, economic policy uncertainty and financial market volatility on the directional movements of clean energy stock prices. It employs a comprehensive analysis of four major ETFs representative of the clean energy industry's performance: PBD, PBW, ICLN, and QCLN. Furthermore, a computational analysis is undertaken by using four well-established machine learning and statistical techniques: Random Forest (RF), XGBoost, Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Naïve Bayes.

At the beginning, this study set out three primary objectives regarding the prediction of clean energy equity prices, all of which have been met. Regarding the first objective concerning the most effective machine learning algorithm for the predictive analysis of clean energy stock prices, this study finds that Random Forest and XGBoost outperform SVM and Naïve Bayes models in terms of accuracy. Specifically, the RF and XGBoost models exhibit strong performance, consistently achieving accuracies of 70% or higher. When the forecasting period is extended to between 15 and 20 days, the RF and XGBoost models maintain their high accuracy, occasionally exceeding 80%, with some datasets, notably QCLN, showcasing accuracy rates above 90%. The SVM model reaches its highest accuracy between 73-75%, whereas the Naïve Bayes model underperforms, achieving an accuracy of only 55-60%. The findings of this study build on the existing body of literature by reinforcing the effectiveness of machine learning techniques, particularly ensemble methods, in accurately predicting stock price movements.

The second and third objectives addressed the significance of features in predictive tasks and examined their variability across the four datasets. The results of the analysis indicate that the technical indicators RSI and MACD are the most important predictor

variables in forecasting the direction of clean energy stock prices. This finding supports existing literature that highlights the significance of using technical indicators in stock price forecasting. In evaluating the importance of non-technical factors, particularly the role of macroeconomic variables in predicting clean energy stock prices, the Economic Policy Uncertainty (EPU) Index and the Volatility Index (VIX) stand out. The significant importance of the VIX aligns with expectations, given that market volatility is a well-known determinant of asset price fluctuations. Conversely, the EPU Index's significance is less intuitive. However, the clean energy sector's sensitivity to changes in energy policy, regulatory adjustments, and government incentives provides a clear explanation for this.

The results presented in this study offer significant implications for a diverse set of stakeholders, including importing and exporting countries, investors, policymakers, and market regulators. Firstly, Random Forest and XGBoost models should be the preferred tools for predicting the direction of clean energy stock prices, given their ability to forecast more accurately than Naïve Bayes and Support Vector Machine (SVM) models. For investors, the choice of model also depends on the specific temporal scope of their trading strategy. Those engaging in short-term trading, might find SVM models to be more aligned with their objectives, given the model's high accuracy in forecasting over a brief span of 0-3 days. In contrast, investors with a medium-term outlook - spanning from 10 to 20 days - would likely benefit from integrating Random Forest or XGBoost into their analytic toolkit. The robust performance and accuracy of these models remains consistent over such an interval, offering a dependable basis for decisions on positions that extend beyond the short term. Secondly, given the significance of technical indicators, notably the Relative Strength Index (RSI) and Moving Average Convergence/Divergence (MACD), investment professionals should include these indicators as definitive features given high variable importance. Moreover, to increase predictive capabilities of models and accurately capture directional movements grounded in economic changes, it is recommended to include features such as the CBOE Volatility Index (VIX) and the Economic Policy Uncertainty Index (EPU). The VIX serves as a barometer of market volatility and investor sentiment, often labelled the "fear gauge", providing valuable insights into market stress levels. The significance of the EPU Index indicates that the clean energy sector is sensitive to policy changes. Policymakers should aim for stable and transparent energy policies to reduce market volatility and foster a stable investment environment. Furthermore, given the sensitivity of clean energy ETFs to the USGG10YR,

policymakers might consider the implications of interest rate changes on clean energy financing. Maintaining low-interest rates could be beneficial to support the sector's growth.

Numerous directions are encouraged for further research. One potential direction would be to broaden the feature space to include different maturities of government yields. Including these variables may offer a more complete picture of how fluctuations in interest rates across the yield curve impact clean energy stock price predictability. Diverse maturities could provide insights into the market's interest rate expectations and term premiums, which are often reflective of the economic climate and investor sentiment. Another possible avenue for future research could involve examining further the interplay between clean energy stock prices and commodity markets, especially those commodities tied to raw materials such as lithium. This research could yield insights into how shifts in the costs of materials used in the construction of renewable infrastructure and assets influence clean energy companies and their market valuations. Additionally, exploring the role of international trade agreements and tariffs in clean energy stock performance could also offer valuable perspectives. Understanding these dynamics can further refine predictive models and aid investors and policymakers in making more informed decisions aligned with global market trends.

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